

Proposed Marketing Strategy and CRM for a Parking Technology Company (Case Study: PT. Oranye)

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ABSTRACT: This research examines issues faced by PT Oranye, a parking technology company in Indonesia, the study focusing on enhancing their marketing strategies and client relationship management (CRM) within the B2B landscape. The main problem identified is the company's struggle to generate sufficient business leads and maintain competitive performance in a post-pandemic market, leading to unsatisfactory revenue achievements. The objective of this study is to analyze the industry perspective and challenges. The research will be utilizing marketing strategies for PT Oranye's improvement in brand awareness and CRM practices to encounter the business issue. The theoretical data analysis is based on strategic management theories such as PESTLE, Porter's Five Forces, and competitor analysis for external factors. Internal factors include VRIO, Marketing 4Ps, Value Chain analysis, and interviews as qualitative research to be structured in a Thematic framework with the objective of obtaining useful findings into effective marketing strategies and CRM standardization to improve business performance. The purpose of the study is also to provide PT Oranye with a comprehensive marketing strategy plan to increase brand awareness and strengthen relationships with both new and existing clients. This involves a detailed examination of the internal and external business environment, stakeholder perceptions, and the competitive landscape.

KEYWORDS: Brand awareness, Digital marketing, Inbound marketing, Client relationship management, Marketing strategy, Parking industry.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia, Southeast Asia's most populous country, consists of thousands of islands with a significant population concentrated in Java, particularly Jakarta. Swift vehicle growth, in averaging 4% annually from 2018 to 2022, has increased the number of vehicles from 121.7 million to 142.5 million. This increase, mainly motorcycles by 87.9%, highlights a substantial opportunity for parking technology and management businesses. The rising demand for efficient parking solutions in major cities underscores the potential for significant revenue in this sector, with numerous companies operating in the field, especially in urban areas like Jakarta.

Figure I. Vehicle Growth (BPS Data 2018 - 2022)

PT Oranye, an innovative parking technology solution provider in Indonesia, has experienced significant obstacles in building a market presence and generating business leads. PT Oranye, established in 2019 and operating since 2020, provides a cloud-based, IoT-driven parking technology management solution that improves efficiency, transparency, and user experience.

Despite technological advancements, the company experiences slow commercial growth and struggle to fulfill business performance target, achieving only 50.67% of its projected revenue in 2023. Furthermore, the findings in the digital channel viewpoint revealed low lead acquisition through online channels and a reduction in website engagement from January to December 2023, indicating inefficient online presence and content. Furthermore, ineffective customer relationship management and a lack of standard procedures delay client acquisition and retention. In spite of a competitive post-COVID-19 market, PT Oranye must increase brand awareness and improve client relationship management strategies to achieve its business goals and sustain long-term success.

The purpose of this study is to investigate and design effective marketing and CRM strategy solutions to improve PT Oranye's brand awareness, customer relationship management, and overall business performance to ensure the company's sustainability and growth in the competitive parking technology industry. PT Oranye has to emphasize the importance of digital channels for marketing and customer engagement. This research has the objectives:

1. To understand business players and owners' perception towards the Parking industry.
2. To understand better the factors that could be used as fundamentals to increase brand awareness for PT Oranye's business permanence.
3. To improve client relationship management's strategy of PT Oranye to new and existing clients.

To answer the research objectives, the author should examine below research questions:

1. How is the perception of parking business players and owners towards the parking industry?
2. What is the marketing strategy that PT Oranye needs to implement in order to improve its business performance?
3. What is the strategy to improve the client relationship management for new and existing clients of PT Oranye?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Inbound marketing is a strategic approach that uses tailored, engaging content to attract potential customers and address their needs. This method, different with traditional marketing, focus on educating customers and building trust to increase brand awareness and generate potential business leads. Inbound marketing focuses on content as an information to fulfill customer needs, helps businesses "create value for a company's brand with less effort" (Kotler and Pfoertsch, 2006).

Figure II. Inbound Marketing Methodology, Source: Hubspot

The beginning of the strategy is started with the Attract stage which focuses on drawing the right audience through valuable content on websites and social media. Continue with the Convert stage turns visitors into leads by collecting information and building relationships. The next stage is Close which businesses may develop leads to finalize sales. After, the Delight stage ensures ongoing engagement and satisfaction, encouraging customers to become promoters through word-of-mouth marketing.

This approach aligns with the digital transformation highlighted in Marketing 4.0, leveraging data analytics to improve strategies and customer engagement. The increasing use of social media in Indonesia, particularly platforms like WhatsApp, Instagram, and Facebook, highlights the importance of these channels in reaching and converting customers. By implementing inbound marketing, businesses can enhance brand awareness, provide comprehensive product information, and generate qualified leads, ultimately fostering long-term customer relationships and driving growth.

Brand awareness, defined as "brand associate", including all knowledge and concepts about the product (*Bilgili and Ozkul, 2015*), is essential to influence customer to have intention of purchasing decisions and build loyalty. Brand associations are linked to brand attributes, the target consumer market, and the benefits that customers require, forming the foundation of brand loyalty and purchasing decisions (*Len, Cind, and Lynn 2007*).

Brand Image is the consumer's perception of the brand and is affected by the information that customers collect about the brand. Prospects' purchasing interest is more prevalent when the brand image is seen positively by consumers. Brand image is a set of beliefs about a certain brand (Kotler and Keller, 2016). Brand image is the customer's perception that existing in their minds, and it is typically related with the product's strength, such as product benefits that distinguish it from competitors. Brand image is created to describe the association and consumer confidence in specific brands (Tjiptono, 2008). Brand image creates company, consumer, and product impressions. It is shaped by consumer feedback and indicators like brand strength, uniqueness, and favorability. Unique features such as appearance, pricing, and unique characters improve brand recognition and compatibility with consumer perceptions (*Shimp, 2014*).

Brand identity is defined as a guidance, purpose, and explanation for the brand, It is further described as "a unique set of brand associations that the brand strategist aspires to create or maintain", which means "these associations represent what the brand stands for and imply a promise to customers from the organization members" (*Aaker, 2010*). A strong brand identity would provide a competitive advantage for the company (*Mindrut et al, 2015*). To avoid confusion, brand identity should be presented effectively, with depth and richness as well as brand identity should be shared throughout the organization and linked to its vision, culture, and values (*Joachimsthaler and Aaker, 1997*).

Figure III. B2B Buying Journey, Source Gartner 2022

B2B Buying journey is a process or steps of customers on purchasing product or services. There are several stages, which started from the problem identification by recognizing a business problem and what should be solved. Continue with solution exploration by researching available information to solutions of the problem. Finding the requirements building by defining specific

product or service features for solutions. Supplier Selection by evaluating potential companies. Validation by confirming the chosen company's solution's fit the problem. Consensus Creation by building stakeholder agreement, and final decision by executing the purchase and implementation. These stages involve internal discussions, research, stakeholder alignment, and overcoming challenges to ensure a successful procurement process (Gartner 2022).

Figure IV. Payne's Five Process Model, Source: Payne & Frow, 2006

Customer Relationship Management, a method for managing relationships with both current and potential consumers, is essential to business success (Pil and Holwelg, 2003). Payne's Five Process Model emphasizes the importance of Strategy Development as the start with a company vision, aiming to expand business. Secondly is value creation by identify and transform value for both customers and the business, focusing on valuable customer segments. Thirdly, multichannel Integration convert all insights into value-adding strategies and activities. Fourthly, performance assessment is needed to evaluate business performance through KPIs, customer satisfaction, and shareholder value. Lastly, having data repository is important in order to collect and analyze customer information to enhance value propositions and CRM effectiveness. These processes guide businesses in creating, assessing, and delivering value efficiently (Payne, 2009). Understanding these theories and models helps to identify ways for improving PT Oranye's business performance, customer relationship management, and overall market positioning.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

The data is collected through interviews, which assisted the researcher in creating a proposed solution. The research framework encompasses both external and internal analyses. External analysis involves PESTLE, Porter's Five Forces, and Competitor Analysis, while internal analysis utilizes VRIO, Marketing Mix 4Ps, and Value Chain Analysis. Strategic formulation is guided by the Five A's and CRM Payne and Frow frameworks, aiming to identify customer loyalty factors and improve CRM. Primary data is gathered through interviews both internal and external stakeholders. Secondary data includes internal company data, journals, articles, books, and institutional reports related.

Data Analysis

The research will be conducted using a descriptive qualitative approach. It describes qualitative research as descriptive, which means that data was gathered in the form of words rather than numbers (Sugiyono, 2010). Five interviews were conducted with PT Oranye's internal and external stakeholders (team members and clients). The interviews were conducted to better understand the parking industry, customer perspectives, business processes, and development of strategies. Internal insights highlight the company's strengths and weaknesses whereas external insights shows market opportunities and threats.

The researcher also gathered secondary data from internal company data (2023 sales report, product features, company profile), journals and articles on inbound marketing and CRM, books on strategic marketing and customer relationships, and institutional reports with demographic and macroeconomic data.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1) External Analysis

PESTLE analysis for PT Oranye identifies key external factors impacting its business.

- Political and Legal: Disintegrated regional parking tax regulations and predetermined parking tariff, this will harm the parking business partnership model of PT Oranye such as revenue or profit share.
- Economic: Core components for software development are in-house built to reduce cost of production.
- Sociocultural: Informal parking and cash payment method habits will increase competition.
- Technological: Technological advancements, Innovation on real-time parking data report allows business owner to check anytime and anywhere. Information source through search engine or any online information.
- Ecological: Potentially more parking business demand for transportation hubs in many areas.

Porter's Five Forces model suggests that competition extends beyond direct competitors. The competition should also consider the company's value which has been created. The company aims to produce value and establish a strategic position to gain competitive advantages. Porter's five forces analysis helps to determine a company's strategy (*Kotler & Armstrong 2016*).

- Threat of New Entrants is considered Low, as the High capital investment required for technology and hardware. Cloud-based model which focuses on data reporting transparency.
- Bargaining Power of Buyers is considered Low, Parking business owners are typically cost-sensitive. Need operational efficiency, and improved customer experience
- Threat of Substitute is considered High, Informal parking offers a cheaper rate with a semi valet service model. However low level of security, and safety which some vehicle owners are not concerned yet.
- Bargaining Power of Suppliers is considered High, PT Oranye relies on an internal technology team, investing in internal software and hardware development to maintain a low reliance on suppliers.
- Rivalry Among Existing Competitors, Few established players. Focus on differentiation through technology innovation and broader target market.

Competitor analysis is to thrive in business, a company must gain and maintain a competitive advantage and superior performance among its competitors, which must be combined into a plan that allows it to quickly switch to achieve superior performance (*Rothaermel, 2021*).

Competitor analysis is necessary to better comprehend competitors' present position.

- Technological Advantage: PT Oranye stands out as the most technologically advanced company among its competitors. This offers an opportunity to attract customers who prioritize features like touchless ticketing, license plate recognition, cloud-based management systems, and EV charging. These features cater to a growing trend of tech-savvy consumers who value convenience and automation.
- Market Differentiation: With its unique features, PT Oranye can differentiate itself in the market. They can target customers who are willing to pay a premium for a more advanced parking experience. This can help them establish a strong brand image and attract a loyal customer base.
- Limited Locations: PT Oranye has the fewest locations compared to its competitors. This can be a significant disadvantage, especially for customers who need parking in a specific area. They may struggle to compete with companies like Secure Parking who offer a wider network.

2) Internal Analysis

Value Chain Analysis, determining a company's value chain for competing in a specific industry is crucial for diagnosing competitive advantage. Value chain analysis is used to break down some activities into ever finer segments as the study reveals distinctions

crucial to competitive advantage (Porter, 1985). The process has two activities that reveal the internal value process which are Primary and Support activities.

Table I. Value Chain Analysis Summary

Primary Activities	Supporting Activities
<p><i>Inbound Logistics:</i> The Finance, Procurement, and Warehouse teams source suppliers for hardware and software components, negotiate rates and lead times, and manage inventory levels efficiently.</p> <p><i>Production:</i> R&D, IT Developers, and Technicians develop new parking technologies, assemble and integrate systems, and handle installation, maintenance, and troubleshooting.</p> <p><i>Outbound Logistics:</i> Procurement, IT Developers, Technicians, and Operations deliver hardware, provide technical support, and train staff on system usage and problem escalation.</p> <p><i>Marketing and Sales:</i> Business Development, Marketing, and Partnership teams conduct market research, promote products, and manage client relationships, though online marketing and business pipeline recording need improvement.</p> <p><i>Services:</i> Client Relations, Technicians, and Operations offer customer support, provide quarterly data analytics reports, and perform monthly software updates and feature enhancements.</p>	<p><i>Organizational Structure:</i> Handles finance, accounting, legal compliance, website maintenance, IT infrastructure, and investment in office and warehouse facilities.</p> <p><i>Personal / HR Management:</i> Recruits and trains staff, enhances product knowledge, and offers professional development opportunities.</p> <p><i>Research & Development:</i> Focuses on developing innovative parking technologies and maintaining partnerships for hardware and software integration.</p> <p><i>Procurement:</i> Sources materials and services at competitive prices, negotiating contracts to ensure quality and timely delivery.</p>

Marketing 4 P's are the company's tactical and controllable marketing tools. Companies use the 4Ps (product, price, place of distribution, and promotion) to target their specific market (Kotler 2017).

Product: PT Oranye specializes in parking technology, offering hardware and software for parking systems with a focus on IoT-based solutions. The company's core products include parking dispensers machine and gate systems, with an additional unique offering called Compact MotorCycle Storage (CMS) product, a vertical parking tower for motorbikes. PT Oranye serves both large-scale customers such as office buildings, hospitals, and malls, and small business owners, offering full management and profit-sharing models or leasing options for parking equipment and software.

Price: PT Oranye's pricing is customizable based on customer needs, ensuring affordability and adaptability to various requirements. The company aims to serve a wide range of clients with competitive prices, influenced by internal development and integration. A standard parking system setup costs around 150 million rupiahs, but prices differ based on specific customer requirements.

Place: PT Oranye's head office and warehouse are in West Jakarta, head office in Kebon Jeruk and all team such as business development, marketing, IT, and R&D teams features a workshop and product displays. The warehouse in Meruya stores parking equipment. customers can see product demonstrations and real showcases like EV charger stations and solar-powered dispensers during office visits.

Promotion: PT Oranye relies on its website and social media for information dissemination but does not focus on digital marketing or advertising. Instead, business leads come from client referrals, supported by an incentive program for referrals. The company plans to enhance its website and utilize social media platforms more effectively in the future but currently lacks a specific digital marketing strategy.

VRIO Analysis, Value, Rarity, Imitability, and Organization. A tool used to evaluate a company's internal resources and capabilities to determine their potential for achieving sustainable competitive advantage. Analyzing PT Oranye's resources using VRIO helps identify strengths and weaknesses that can sustain its market position. The analysis of PT Oranye's resources based on four criteria. Value determines if a resource adds worth by enabling the company to exploit opportunities or fend off threats. Rarity assesses if the resource is scarce or unique among current and potential competitors. Inimitability evaluates how easily competitors can replicate the resource or capability. Organization considers if the company is structured and managed to fully utilize the resource's potential. PT Oranye's Parking Management System excels in all four criteria, offering sustainable competitive advantage, while other resources provide only competitive parity due to their commonality and ease of imitation.

I. Thematic Framework

Thematic code and description is created based on the result of the qualitative interview to support the external and internal data collection and analysis. The objective of the framework finding codes that are related to the research objectives. The table below shows interviewee scripts that show relevance of the research function.

Table II. Thematic Codes and Description

Theme	Codes	Description
Perceptions of the Parking Industry	Industry Challenges, Industry Opportunities, Regulatory Impact	Regulatory difficulty include different tax regulations and parking tariff in each region in which difficult to maximize the revenue (Noviyanti). Illegal parking management involves locals and mass organizations protecting illegal parking areas (Ridwan). Industry Opportunities: Demand for parking technology remains strong with PT Oranye's technological innovations (Noviyanti).
Marketing Strategies	Marketing Activities, Brand Awareness	Offline strategies involve canvassing and distributing business cards and booklets at buildings (Rara) is not fully effective. Online presence includes using a website and social media for product and service information (Karina) could be a useful tool. Digital Marketing: PT Oranye currently lacks a specific digital marketing plan (Karina). Brand Awareness: PT Oranye is still not sufficient compared to established companies like Secure Parking or CentrePark (Karina).
Client Relationship Management	Client Acquisition Process, Client Retention Strategies, Communication Effectiveness, Service Improvement	Information of business lead is usually gathered from client network or previous work relationships (Rara). Client Retention Strategies: Regular check-ins occur every 1-2 months to maintain relationships (Rara). Communication Effectiveness: Tools like telephone, email, and WhatsApp are used for follow-ups (Noviyanti). Issues arise when clients feel ignored (Noviyanti). Service Improvement: Quick responses are crucial, and the BD team is attentive due to PT Oranye being a new company (Ridwan).
Innovation and Technology	Product Innovation, Technology Integration, Unique Value Proposition	Unique solutions include CMS for multi-level motorcycle parking and an IoT cloud-based reporting system (Noviyanti). Unique Value Proposition: Real-time data access allows remote report checks, eliminating daily ro weekly travel (Ridwan).
Operational and Economic Factors	Operational Efficiency, Economic Impact	Local challenges mean it takes 3-6 months for a parking lot to be fully operational (Ridwan). Economic Impact: The price of machinery from China is stable (Noviyanti), and pricing is flexible to meet parking building requirements (Wilman).

SWOT analysis is used to gain insights from combination of internal and external analysis as well as the interview result. A SWOT analysis evaluates a company's current and future prospects by taking into account both internal and external elements. PT Oranye has the following SWOTs:

Table III. SWOT Analysis

Strength	Weakness
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> In-house development for parts and systems. IoT cloud-based software for real-time parking data report. Exclusive CMS model patent enhancing brand value. Customizable pricing model. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of digital marketing strategy for new leads. Inconsistent customer relationship management business model. Low brand recognition and low locations.
Opportunity	Threat
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Cost reduction via in-house hardware and software development. New parking hubs near train stations. Untapped market parking expansion through digital channels. New CRM approach for business improvement. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Different regional tax regulations. Increased competition from informal parking. High costs for advanced technology and marketing. Competitors with superior service and CRM.

TOWS strategic formulation matrix, potential resources in PT Oranye will be identified. This matrix brings together key matching techniques to assist company in developing four types of strategies. A combination of SWOT and TOWS are crucial elements to strategies weaknesses and threats and also maximizing strengths and opportunities over the next five years (Ravanavar and Charantimath, 2012).

Table IV. TOWS Matrix

Strength – Opportunity (SO)	Weakness – Opportunity (WO)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leverage in-house hardware and software to reduce costs and increase competitiveness. (S1, S2, O1) Expand to parking hubs with customizable pricing and promote the CMS model for efficiency. (S3, S4, O2) Untapped parking expansion with online channels, highlighting IoT for transparency and real-time data. (S2, O3, O4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance digital marketing (SEO, social media) to improve brand awareness and market expansion. (W1, W3, O3) Standardize CRM processes to improve lead conversion and customer satisfaction. (W2, O3, O4) Boost brand recognition through collaborations with parking hubs. (W1, W3, O2)
Strength – Threat (ST)	Weakness – Threat (WT)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In-house development capabilities for better feature over informal parking and advanced revenue reporting. (S1, S2, T2, T3) Utilize the patent-protected CMS model to prevent imitation and manage regional tax variations. (S3, T1, T2) Optimize in-house development to manage high capital investments and enhance cost efficiency. (S1, S4, T3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve digital marketing to boost brand recognition and competitiveness. (W1, W3, T2, T4) Standardize CRM to enhance retention and brand perception. (W2, T4) Utilize technical capabilities for internal software and marketing improvements. (W1, W2, T3) Increase customer locations to mitigate regional tax and tariff. (W3, T1)

To address the business solutions for PT Oranye, the SWOT analysis and TOWS matrix serve as essential tools to translate strategic insights into actionable marketing strategies and customer relationship management (CRM) improvements. This change of strategy aligns with the company's goals of increasing market penetration and improving customer relations. By bridging the SWOT and TOWS analysis into specific marketing and CRM strategies, PT Oranye may leverage its strengths, address its weaknesses, seize opportunities, and reduce threats to achieve a competitive edge in the parking technology industry.

Inbound Marketing Strategy, based on the SWOT analysis, PT Oranye's marketing strategy should focus on several key areas to increase brand awareness and market reach. Additionally, PT Oranye could leverage its strengths in in-house hardware and software development to offer unique value propositions. Highlighting these technological advantages in marketing campaigns can differentiate the company from competitors. Promoting the IoT cloud-based software for real-time data reporting and customizable pricing models can appeal to potential clients looking for innovative parking solutions. **(SO1, WO1, WT1, WT3)**

1. Website design and content improvement for potential customers products and services exploration. **(SO1, WO1, WT1)**
2. Focus on SEO (Search Engine Optimization) for search engine rankings. **(WO1, WT1)**
3. Focus on Regularly create media content to increase visibility to broader audience. **(WO1, WT1, WT3)**
4. Run ads campaign to boost brand recognition and generate leads. **(WO1, WT1)**

CRM (Customer Relationship Management) standardization and optimization is crucial for PT Oranye to maintain and expand its customer base. The SWOT analysis revealed gaps in the standardization of client relationship management processes. **(WO2, WT2)**

1. To apply CRM Payne's Five Process Model. **(WO2, WT2)**
2. Use CRM Tools for better tracking and customer analysis. **(WO2, WT2)**

Partnership to boost competitive positioning "recommendation". **(SO2, SO3, WO3, ST1, ST2, WT4)**

1. Collaborate with existing commuter companies (KRL/LRT/MRT) to promote transport hub for brand awareness improvement. **(SO2, WO3, ST2)**
2. Highlight the CMS model and IoT cloud-based for brand recognition. **(SO3, ST1, ST3)**

Business Solution

The research on PT Oranye case, addresses challenges related to marketing strategies and client relationship management (CRM) within the B2B landscape. The study emphasizes to enhance brand awareness and improve its CRM practice to achieve better business performance in a competitive parking industry. Therefore, in conclusion six advises that PT Oranye should immediately implement to improve its marketing efforts, and CRM practice improvement, and positioning itself for continuous success in the competitive parking industry.

1. Enhance Digital Marketing: Implement SEO, social media activities, and educational content for brand awareness and online presence.
2. Standardize CRM Processes: Utilize CRM practices to improve customer data utilization, lead conversion, and customer satisfaction.
3. Leverage In-House Capabilities: Focus on in-house hardware and software development to reduce costs and increase competitiveness.
4. Optimize Technical Capabilities: Use advanced revenue reporting and cashless payment models to differentiate from parking competitors.
5. Untapped market: Target new parking hubs near train stations with customizable pricing and promote the patented CMS model for motorcycles.
6. Boost Brand Recognition: Collaborate with transit systems (LRT/MRT/KRL) to enhance visibility and brand recognition.

Implementation Plan & Justification

The implementation timeframe for PT Oranye starts from July to September which covers Website Design, SEO, Social Media, and CRM Tool actions. Graphic design begins in July, followed by content creation in mid-July and a launch date of early August. SEO begins in late July, with Google Ads running into August. Social media activities, including slide and video creation, will begin in July, with paid advertising being reviewed biweekly and monthly. CRM Tool searches and demos begin in early July, with usage and data transfer beginning in mid-July. This strategy improves consumer interaction and operational efficiency while taking advantage of low-cost online platforms for growth.

Table II. Implementation Timeline in Q3 2024

Activities		July				August				September			
		W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4
Website Design	Design (Visual)	█	█	█				█				█	
	Content (product & services)	█	█	█				█				█	
	Contact form	█	█	█				█	█			█	█
	Final Review and Launch			█	█			█	█			█	█
SEO	Keyword Research				█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
	Content review & analysis				█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
	Google Paid Ads							█					█
Social Media	Slide (content) picture	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
	Video	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
	Paid ads		█	█	█		█	█		█	█	█	█
	Socmed review & analysis				█			█				█	█
CRM tool	Search CRM tool	█	█										
	Product demo	█	█										
	CRM Utilization & Socialization		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
	Data Transfer		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Integrating strategic formulations into PT Oranye's marketing and CRM operations is essential for addressing existing business issues and capitalizing on new potential customers. Implementing an inbound marketing approach will increase online visibility and traffic by optimizing website design, SEO, and creating informative material for social media. Digital advertising will increase brand recognition and deliver high-quality leads. CRM Payne's Five Process Model will simplify company workflows and improve relationships with customers by allowing more effective tracking, customer analysis, and data-driven decision-making.

To maintain a competitive edge, it is essential to continuously optimize SEO and social media, establish business partnerships, use technology advantages for EV charging stations, and improve CRM procedures. These efforts will boost PT Oranye's market presence, strengthen relationships with customers, and promote long-term growth in the parking technology business. Integrating inbound marketing with CRM technologies will improve brand exposure, market share, and long-term success.

As a new player competing with established enterprises, PT Oranye must develop a successful marketing strategy to express its unique value propositions, build strong client relationships, and improve repeat business. By focusing on competitive positioning, technological advantages, and client acquisition and retention, PT Oranye may achieve its business goals and establish a strong reputation. Strategic partnerships with commuter companies like as KRL, LRT, and MRT might help PT Oranye increase a competitive advantage and improve its image. Promoting the Compact Motorcycle Storage (CMS) model and IoT cloud-based solutions will set PT Oranye apart from competitors. Collaboration with PLN to construct low-cost EV charging stations for motorbikes will benefit green initiatives and strengthen PT Oranye's position in sustainable transportation in cities.

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